

STRATEGIC ANALYSIS OF THE EXTERNAL ENVIRONMENT OF "STEKLOPLASTIK" LLC

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Abstract. *In this article, the main factors of success that are crucial for determining the main economic characteristics and driving forces of development in the enterprise, assessing the level of competition and determining the competitive position of industrial enterprises, forecasting and improving development prospects are considered.*

Keywords: *enterprise, market, environment, competition, valuation, factor, demand, supply.*

INTRODUCTION. The furniture and woodworking industry of Uzbekistan is one of the rapidly developing industries in our country. If 5-8 years ago, 65-70% of the domestic market of our country was made up of products of foreign manufacturers, today about 90% of the market capacity is satisfied with high-quality domestic products. More than 1,100 furniture production and assembly enterprises operate in the republic, 500 of them are established in Tashkent.

The furniture and wood processing industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the fastest growing industries in our country. If in previous years 65-70% of the country's domestic furniture market was filled with the products of foreign manufacturers, today more than 90% of the demand is satisfied with high-quality furniture products produced in our country. During 2003-2016, the volume of production in the industry increased 16 times, and in the last five years, the growth rate of production has been accelerating. Today, more than 6,000 enterprises are operating in the field of furniture and wood processing across the country. These include the creation of finished furniture products, preparation of furniture raw materials, production of various accessories, production of semi-finished products, includes enterprises such as primary processing of wood. The general analysis shows that Tashkent city and five regions of the republic are leading in furniture production, namely Tashkent, Fergana, Samarkand, Namangan and Kashkadarya regions. These regions account for 80% of furniture production. Recently, furniture production has been developing widely in Jizzakh and Navoi provinces. Furniture production enterprises are of great importance in meeting the daily needs of the people of our country and in creating decent living conditions in residential areas. Furniture is needed for any new home or social facility, so as the economy develops, the demand for furniture will increase.

By the end of the year, the total area in our country is 12,078.1 thousand square meters. residences have been built and commissioned. We should take into account that all this is equipped with kitchen, bedroom, soft and other types of furniture. In January-December 2022, 311,400 marriages were registered by the registry office, which means certain furniture will be purchased for so many new families. Analyzing the development of the social sphere, modern hospitals with 6,032 beds, polyclinics with 19,368 visits, general education and specialized schools with 77,436 student places were built during the year. Each built object requires specialized furniture. In addition, capital renovated objects,

In 2021 - 2022, the comparative graph of furniture production volumes in the republic is presented in the following figure. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Changes in the volume of furniture production in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021-2022, billion soums.

Figure 2. Changes in physical volumes of furniture production in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021-2022, %.

As of January 1, 2022, 6094 enterprises were operating in our republic, of which 493 are located in Samarkand region, 1320 in Tashkent city, and 628 in Andijan region.

An overview of the state of the industry includes identifying its main economic characteristics and driving forces of development, assessing the level of competition and determining the competitive position of industrial enterprises, forecasting the prospects for development and searching for key success factors that are crucial for improvement. . The competitive position in this field depends on many external factors. Therefore, we use the PESTEL-matrix method, which is widely used in strategic marketing, to study the factors affecting the furniture watch. (Table 1)

Table 1

PESTEL analysis of the furniture market of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Political	NEW Constitution; Political stability;	Economical	Increase in public welfare; Increase in income;
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	Global competition; Cooperation with neighboring countries; Activity of political blocs in the world;		Raw material prices; Risks of doing business; Credit policy;
Social	Multi-storey construction; Social development programs; Increase the welfare of the people; Demographic policy;	Technological	Wood processing technology; Creation of NEW materials; Modern requirements for furniture design; Complexity and cost of equipment.
Ecological	Green spaces policy; Environmental standards of the product; Production restrictions; International climate requirements.	Legal	Laws and Presidential Decrees; Business environment; Business benefits; Export support

The first place in the world furniture market is occupied by US manufacturers (23.16%), and the second place is occupied by China (14.74%). 73% of furniture production is occupied by ten developed countries. As a result, the level of competition in the international furniture market is very strong. Political factors include the implementation of the open door policy by the President of our country, which means that today our country is open to all political forces.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results Social factors. Factors determining consumption trends in the furniture and wood products market are:

1. Urbanization. In 2008, the share of the world's urban population exceeded 50 percent, and by 2020, this figure will reach 55 percent, and in 2050, it is expected to reach 70 percent. Urbanization trends in Uzbekistan generally follow global trends.

2. The situation in the real estate market. If in the last 2 years there has been a decrease or a slight increase in housing prices in developed countries, due to the propensity of the population to invest, prices in the real estate market in Uzbekistan are increasing. State investment programs support these trends.

3. Social changes in society help to change the composition of households, communal services, social infrastructure objects and reduce the number of their participants. With the general increase in the number of households, in line with the trends in developed countries, the share of those headed by one or two persons is increasing.

4. Change in the way of consumption of durable goods, including furniture. Now, more and more people pay attention not only to the functionality of a certain piece of furniture, but also to its architectural and aesthetic aspects when buying furniture in trade organizations of our country. Consumers are attracted to furniture with high-quality visual features that meet the requirements of modernity, unlike what was presented on the market a few years ago. As a result of the development of the new consumption model, only 20% of consumers indicated that they would buy furniture in the long term. The remaining 80% of consumers do not extend the service life of furniture beyond 5-8 years.

Technological factors. Experts call home building one of the most popular new technologies in furniture production. It was developed about 20 years ago and is widely used all over the world. However, if house building is very actively used in Australia, the USA, Israel and other countries, local companies have increased their interest in it in recent years, and today it is becoming especially relevant.

The placement technology itself in furniture production ensures processing of the entire sheet of material in only one hole in the machining center using the maximum number of operations. As a result, the production of furniture is significantly simplified and accelerated, the production process becomes cheaper and the amount of waste is minimized.

Advantages of technology. Specific features of using new equipment depend on the features of a particular production. Its effectiveness is affected by the flexibility of the production process, the need to optimize cutting, serial production and their quantity. Using this technology, the process of combined wardrobe furniture, for example, corridors with a corner wardrobe, and frames for soft products, for example, sofas for the kitchen or living room, armchairs, etc. In addition, the advantages of the technology include: reduce the total time of product production; reduce transportation and storage costs; increase the accuracy and quality of operations by automating production; saving raw materials due to optimization of material cutting.

Environmental factors. Furniture production is a rapidly developing and promising industry. Furniture production is one of the main processes of using wood. In the production of furniture, materials, wooden blanks are used, which are divided into cut and glued. The main problem is that the technological processes of furniture production are associated with the release of harmful substances into the atmosphere: dust, vapors of solvents and thinners, formaldehyde, carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxide, ammonia, wood waste. The main sources of atmospheric pollution in furniture enterprises include: finishing, gluing and covering, plywood and drying shops, as well as chipboard and plywood processing.

The production process of furniture production is a set of all processes related to the transformation of raw materials and materials entering the enterprise into finished products. It includes the direct impact of machines, tools and labor on the raw materials and materials from which the product is made. The main stages of the technological process of furniture production are drying wood, cutting it, processing rough blanks, gluing and veneering them, processing finished blanks, assembling parts into units, assembly of processing units, finishing aggregates and parts and is to collect them. product.

During sawing, varnishing and sanding, wood and varnish dust is removed. The furniture company is characterized by the presence of technological emissions of harmful substances into the atmosphere. Process wastes include tail wastes, equipment blasting wastes, process furnace

flues. Technological emissions are characterized by a high concentration of small amounts of harmful substances.

Emissions of substances such as ammonia, methylchloroform, and carbon monoxide lead to climate change, destruction of the ozone layer, and an increase in the transparency of the atmosphere, which causes the greenhouse effect. All this indicates that the production of wooden furniture pollutes the atmosphere in the process of sawing, cooking, gluing, and painting. Also, it has a negative impact on the health of workers and causes the risk of cancer and other oncological diseases.

Technological processes with open production cycles are used to reduce the anthropogenic impact of furniture production on the human environment and ecology. In this case, waste from production is cleaned using filters. It is an expensive technology, and only rarely can the cost of waste materials cover the costs of building and operating wastewater treatment plants. The following protection methods are used to reduce the negative impact of harmful substances on human health:

1. Excluding the contact of the harmful substance with the working person. This can be achieved through mechanization and automation of production processes, sealing equipment.
2. Use of personal protective equipment, such as overalls, respiratory protection, special ointments for skin protection.
3. Compliance with hygiene standards in the production area, timely ventilation.

Harmful vapors and gaseous emissions are removed from the exhaust air in the following ways: absorption by solid porous materials, chemical transformation of harmful substances into less harmful substances, neutralization in chemical neutralizers.

In order to minimize the consequences of severe environmental pollution, it is necessary to actively introduce clean technologies that significantly increase life expectancy; development of science-intensive technologies, using computerization on a large scale; improvement of environmental legislation with lasting effect.

The conducted analysis shows that office furniture occupies only more than 9% of the total furniture market needs.

In this regard, there are not many competitors of "Stekloplastik" LLC in the Samarkand region. If we evaluate the competition according to the characteristics of "assortment-specialization", we can see the following.

Table 2

Strategic map of competitors on the "specialization-assortment" signs in the furniture market of Samarkand region

wide	LLC "Gulobod Mebel"	LLC "Garant Furniture"	LLC "Steklo plastic"	
medium	LLC "Asia Furniture"	Davr Mebel LLC	NPO "El holding"	LLC "ART FURNITURE"
narrow	LLC "Magnum furniture"	LLC "Brand furniture"	LLC "Aziyza Sport",	"ZABARDAST FURNITURE"

Assortment / specialization	Soft furniture	Kitchen furniture	Special furniture	Components
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As can be seen from these data, there is specialization in the types of furniture products in large furniture enterprises, that is, enterprises specializing in soft furniture can include LLC "Gulobod Mebel", LLC "Asiyo Mebel", LLC "Magnum Mebel". Among the manufacturers of kitchen furniture, we can mention "Garant Mebel" LLC, "Davr Mebel" LLC, and "Brand Mebel" LLC. Similarly, the role of custom furniture manufacturers and component manufacturers can be identified.

At the next stage of our analysis, it will be shown in the form of a strategic map according to the "price-quality" characteristics of the enterprises in the special furniture market. Since it is difficult to collect information about competitors, we determined this strategic map by conducting a survey among specialists of "Stekloplastik" LLC. All competitors are included in the survey and their indicators are compared to each other (Table 3)

Table 3.

Assessment of competition in the special furniture market in Samarkand region

Name of competitor	Regarding "STEKLOPLASTIK" LLC		
	Assortment(wide or narrow)	Quality(high, medium, low)	Prices(high, equal, low)
LLC "AZIZA SPORT",	narrow	low	high
LLC "ART FURNITURE"	narrow	medium	low
LLC "MAGNUM MEBEL",	narrow	tall	low
LLC "GARANT MEBEL",	wide	tall	high
LLC "BRAND MEBEL",	wide	medium	high
LLC "ZABARDAST MEBEL" auto repair shop,	narrow	low	medium
LLC "KRONOMAX",	narrow	medium	high
KK "MEHAU",	narrow	medium	high
KK LLC "ULTIMA",	narrow	tall	high
LLC "DAVR MEBEL",	wide	medium	high
LLC "OTABEK",	narrow	tall	medium
LLC "GULOBAD MEBEL",	wide	tall	high
LLC "NURFAYOZ MEBELLARI",	narrow	low	low
LLC "ASIYO MEBEL"	wide	medium	medium
NPO "EL HOLDING"	narrow	medium	high

As a result of the survey, it was found that there are 16 potential competitors of the enterprise, of which only five are considered direct or close competitors. These include LLC "Aziyza Sport", LLC "El Holding", LLC "Otabek", LLC "Magnum Mebel" and LLC "Nurfayoz Furniture". The maebel range they produce is similar to the company under analysis. Based on this, we will create a strategic map of the "price-quality" competitor of "Stekloplastik" LLC (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Strategic map of competitors in the market of special furniture according to "price-quality" characteristics.

1- LLC "Aziyza sport", 2- NPO "El holding", 3- LLC "Stekloplastik", 4- LLC "Otabek", 5- LLC "Magnum furniture", 6- LLC "Nurfayoz furniture"

As can be seen from this picture, Stekloplastik LLC is far superior to its close competitors in terms of production volume. Prices are also average among competitors. At the same time, some competitors are superior to "Stekloplastik" LLC in terms of quality. This gives the company new strategic tasks.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The rapid reforms being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan are encouraging the further development of the views and attitudes towards entrepreneurship among our people. Today, 523,600 business entities are operating in our country, they have achieved the production of a large part of the gross domestic product. Entrepreneurial activity has a positive impact on real sectors of our economy. In some production areas, business entities pay 100%. One such industry is the furniture industry. Today, more than 6,000 enterprises in the sector are all private businesses. The strategy of Sokha enterprises affects the state and trends of the furniture market.

The conducted theoretical and practical researches are dedicated to the modern trends of marketing strategy and are carried out on the example of "Stekloplastik" LLC. The results of research are the basis for the following conclusions.

Scientific and methodological research in modern marketing theory practically shows the priority of strategic thinking in this discipline. The continuous improvement of strategic marketing methods and approaches within the science is the basis for new methods and processes in today's marketing. One of these is the methodology of strategic analysis.

The development of marketing in industrial enterprises leads to the formation of a strategic marketing system in management. It is possible to demonstrate the application of strategic planning stages, the use of strategic marketing principles, and the organization of strategic analysis departments.

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